

A SHORT PRESENTATION OF VOLUME MATERIALS

Viktoriya Karpukhina proposes an interpretation of the linguistic reality in the cognitive-discursive aspect. The phenomena under consideration are the objects of the linguistic reality (a text, a discourse, an intertext, a hypertext). The author studies the scientific paradigms viewing through the epistemological triad "tradition – modern – postmodern". She reveals the most important aspects of studying the linguistic reality objects in the scientific paradigms turn during the 20-21st centuries.

In her article **Stella Gorbani** makes an attempt to analyze the structure, meaning and the functions of the parenthetic elements in three different languages, paying attention to the similarities and differences these structures have in English, Romanian and Russian.

The research of **Gergana Atanassova Petkova** deals with some Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names Latin by origin, canonized by the Catholic Church. The observation is implemented on the corpus of fifty-three feminine anthroponyms.

Luminița Hoarță Cărașu explores the doctor-patient communication as a particular type of dialogue. This type of communication implies an institutional setting (as for example, a hospital or a clinic). The communication under analysis involves the act of pre-assigning the sender's role. Indeed, the doctor-patient communication evolves taking into consideration the participants' social statuses, whereas, the doctor's social status governs the act of communication imposing the concrete topic of the verbal interaction. The paper analyzes the way in which the topic is interrelated with the institutional setting where the communication unfolds.

Daniela Maria Marțole's paper focuses upon the representation of the body, as constitutive of the self, in the play "Macbeth", by W. Shakespeare. Considering some critical perspectives upon the play, the paper insists upon the body exterior, dissected/mutilated as the object of knowledge the main means towards the discovery and understanding of the body interior, a network of energies generally neglected in the early modern culture.

Anamaria Grecu-Gheorghiu studies the occasional sermons (paraenesis) as a separate homiletic genre, distinct from the other forms of speech acknowledged in specialized orthodox writings.

The cultural practice of tea drinking played an important part in the Victorian lifestyle. Inside a Victorian house, the roles of husband and wife were clearly established through (un)written rules, and men and women were expected to behave in certain ways. Organizing and conducting a tea drinking party, as well as coordinating the setting of the table for a private family tea gathering, or just for the purpose of having one or two guests over tea, was the task of Victorian wives. **Ioana Boghian's** paper attempts to identify the functions of the Victorian cultural practice of tea drinking.

Solomija Buk proposes a quantitative analysis of Ivan Franko's novel "Without Asking a Wade". The statistical features of the novel are obtained on the basis of text corpus. A special attention is paid to quantitative relations between parts of speech (the indexes of epithetization, nominalization, and verbal definitions).

Sergey Stroykov reviews the E. Ungureanu's book "Dincolo de text: HYPERTEXTUL" which contains a profound linguistic analysis of a conceptual triad: text - intertext - hypertext.

Luiza Şoşu proposes a translation in English of Mihai Eminescu's *Hesperus*.